

The Social Evolution Journey of African American Community

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Abstract

The present research paper attempts to investigate the social evolution journey of African-American people by revisiting select African-American autobiographies. The African American community has a long and complex history which expresses the struggle, resilience, and transformation of African-American population in America. By evaluating the African-American autobiographies a close observation is to be conducted to explore the times of hardship, resilience, and change throughout the rich and complicated history of the African American population in the United States. Mainly this paper will highlight the social evolution journey of black population who suffered for generations to achieve human status in the society. Taking into consideration of pain and pathetic lives of these people this paper aims to examine their historical events, social movements, and cultural milestones from social evolution perspective. It also provides a comprehensive understanding of the African American experience and its impact on American society through the autobiographies.

Keywords: Blacks, African-American, Social Evolution, Race, Slavery, etc.

Introduction:

The social evolution journey of African-American community from slavery to self-made human remains an ignored topic of research. It discloses the historical, cultural, political, and economic evolution of black population from several generations. Through the slave trade from the history we can come to know the struggle and experiences of black people for the equality. This particular research paper attempts to explore the social evolution journey of Black communities by examining minute historical marks, cultural shifts and socio-political movements that have redefined identity, hierarchy, and collective progress of black and white population.

In the 16th and 17th century the forced transposition and enslavement of African population has made the initiation of the systematic racial discrimination which has impacted the society for subsequent generations. Right from the history these black population had faced oppression through political rules and Jim Crow acts. Abolition of slavery remained the untrue dream in those days. Political rules against the black population created the huge safety for the white dominance. All the rules and acts have been created against the black population. They have been considered only the slave of the country. It took many years to abolish the slavery system with legal help.

Though, despite having the systemic barriers by the white dominance blacks have consistently demonstrated the commitment to the social progress. Result of this there are numerous historical evidences of such activities. Movements such as The Harlem Renaissance in the United States and anti-colonial liberation movements in Africa are the major epitome contemporary time. Through these movements the global influence of figures like Martin Luther King Jr, Nelson Mandela and Malcolm X created the Awareness in the people. These activists have illustrated the power of collective action in challenging systemic injustices in African and America. These movements have challenged the socio-political concerns against the racial discrimination. Various movements and political activism has played a vital role in the social evolution of black population. Through the genres such as jazz, blues, reggae, hip-hop has transcended cultural boundaries, serving as vehicles for storytelling, resistance, and empowerment. It also helped to highlights the social evolution journey of black people. Recent decades witnessed the evolution of blacks from social points of view. Globalization and digital technology have amplified the voices of Black communities, fostering global solidarity and shared cultural experiences. Social media movements such as #BlackLivesMatter have transcended national boundaries, highlighting ongoing racial injustices while mobilizing people worldwide in solidarity. All these things claim that this community have gone through the severe social evolution journey. The social evolution journey of black people who lives in America can be analysed as follows. The minute analysis of the social evolution journey of black people depicts how the evolution took place over a period. This paper aims to proposed some of the social evolution stages of black lives.

Social Evolution of African-American People:

Some of the social evolution stages in the journey are,

1. Animal Stage:

The slave trade has made the black people animals for the white dominance. The entire

dominance had no objection to make another human being animal. Rather they feel happy that they have found something to maintain their lives. The brutal tradition of the slave trade made the generations of the blacks animals. They faced animal like treatment by the white dominant society. The slave trade have forcibly transported blacks as animals from one place to another. The trade used to take place in many of European markets like London, France and American territories. These markets openly allowed the slave trade as animals sell and buy through the legal market trades. Blacks have no importance than an animal for the white to work in the farms. Smallwood says, "Beginning in the 16th century, this trade subjected Africans to severe physical and psychological trauma. The horrors of the Middle Passage, where enslaved Africans were transported in inhumane conditions, are well-documented" (Smallwood 72). Right from the 16th century animal like treatment has offered the blacks in America. No importance as a human being and buy and sell like animals makes this entire population as animal. African Americans who were enslaved faced hard labor, terrible punishments, and significant limitations on their freedom. Such treatment none other than encourages us to analyse the blacks as animals. Captivating blacks remained to work as at farm and white owner's house.

2. Slavery Stage:

Slavery is a contemporary tactic used to maintain marginalization under prevailing laws. The origin of slavery has a pretty straightforward explanation. Following a significant time when the dominant class required help in their lives, they began to view members of the marginal class as having certain limitations. In their civilization, the dominant class need laborers, farmers, cleaners, and workers. Marginals were the only simple choice. The marginals so turn into slaves. As society moved forward, Black people and those from lower castes gained acceptance. Slavery, however, was not the answer for the underprivileged. Even they have to gone through the severe time where they have opened another horrible chapter of discrimination.

The traces of slavery date back to 3500 B.C., when slavery was a widespread practice among all dominants. Slavery was recognized by the US Constitution in the 17th and 18th centuries. In the past, African enslaved people were abducted and made to labor on rice, tobacco, and indigo plantations in the United States. Only the marginals have been able to meet the needs of the upper class and white dominants. White societies are developed through the usage of kidnapped Black people. They were unimportant as human beings, nevertheless. In the past, slaves worked to improve the prevailing society. Dominants, however, have never acknowledged their significance. They lived their entire lives in affluence.

3. Awareness of Owns own Situation:

Numerous activists of Black communities began speaking out against the injustices and humiliation in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. People on the margins of society began to realize that they were being treated unfairly and that they needed to be freed from all forms of power. They became aware of their pitiful situation and how they are controlled and prevented from leading fulfilling lives as human beings. Their realisation of their own situation made them to be agitated. Consequently they become aware and start fighting fr their won fundamental rights. Activists like Nelson Mandela made this whole population to be aware of their situation. "We are slave in our own country. We are tenants on our own soil. We have no strength, no power, no control over our own destiny in the land of our birth". (Mandela. 28) The height of injustice caused those in poverty to reflect on their own pitiful situation. Here, Mandela strongly emphasized how his people are accustomed to the prevailing society. They are not valued as human beings in their own country. Who are they? They must protest and challenge the status quo in order to be accepted as human in their culture.

4. Education:

The most powerful stage occurred in the journey of social evolution of blacks is education. It has changed the lives of black people. Through the education blacks have achieved the sense of identity. "Enslaved individuals created vibrant communities, maintained oral histories, and practiced religious rituals that provided solace and a sense of identity". (Blassingame 152). Education made these people to think about the pathetic life. Through the education several blacks have showed their mettle and achieve the respect in the society. Due to their qualities in various filed they proved the point that they are also humans and they need the human like treatment.

5. Socially Respected:

Marginals were limited to their neighborhood because of the lack of freedom. Although he was highly intelligent, only his own village and society recognized him. However, becoming respected and socially acceptable in society at large was not that far off. In the past, African American and Indian marginals were not even acknowledged as human, but today they are socially valued and accepted for their abilities and behavioral patterns. We have a long list of individuals who have shown the world their extraordinary intelligence and who uphold community justice. They became famous as a model for society because of their efforts to uplift the underprivileged and combat human practices. Taking those names first in a line like that is really challenging. Each person's exuberant personality toward equality and human freedom in society is displayed.

Conclusion

The social evolution journey of African American people offers to understand the pathetic lives of African-American people. they faced severe discrimination over a period and gone through the pathetic social evolution journey to achieve the civilised status in the society as a human beings. The above mentioned stages are the sample stages that have faced by blacks while achieving the civilised status. Eventually, we have to admire that these community have gone through the social evolution journey.

Works Cited

1. Blassingame, John W. *The Slave Community: Plantation Life in the Antebellum South*. Oxford University Press, 1979.
2. Branch, Taylor. *Parting the Waters: America in the King Years 1954-63*. Simon & Schuster, 1988.
3. Carson, Clayborne. *In Struggle: SNCC and the Black Awakening of the 1960s*. Harvard University Press, 1981.
4. Dyson, Michael Eric. *The Black Presidency: Barack Obama and the Politics of Race in America*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 2016.

5. Foner, Eric. *Reconstruction: America's Unfinished Revolution, 1863-1877*. Harper & Row, 1988.
6. Garza, Alicia. *The Purpose of Power: How We Come Together When We Fall Apart*. One World, 2020.
7. Huggins, Nathan Irvin. *Harlem Renaissance*. Oxford University Press, 1971.
8. Lemann, Nicholas. *The Promised Land: The Great Black Migration and How It Changed America*. Vintage Books, 1991.
9. Mandela, Nelson. *Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*. United States, Little, Brown, 2008.
10. Smallwood, Stephanie E. *Saltwater Slavery: A Middle Passage from Africa to American Diaspora*. Harvard University Press, 2007.
11. Woodward, C. Vann. *The Strange Career of Jim Crow*. Oxford University Press, 1955.